

Processing Agroforestry Walnuts into High-Value Oil

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Walnuts ready for processing

Agroforestry is an agricultural system in which woody perennials or shrubs are combined with crops or livestock. Rows of walnut trees are particularly suitable for agroforestry, both in combination with livestock and with arable crops. The sale and processing of walnut products can provide an alternative source of income and appeal to a customer segment that values sustainable and locally produced food. The increasing interest in ecologically responsible and regional products has revived walnut cultivation in Belgium. Although walnut trees have been part of the Belgian landscape for centuries, the majority of the walnuts consumed and processed here are imported. This situation is gradually changing, with a growing number of local producers focusing on walnut cultivation and processing. The sale of freshly harvested walnuts is the least labor-intensive option, but further processing and valorization of the entire walnut can generate higher returns. Although the production of walnut oil requires investments, this process offers additional sales opportunities. Walnut oil has a variety of uses, both for consumption and for cosmetic purposes, and is known for its healthy fatty acids and nutritional value. The production process begins with the harvesting and drying of the walnuts. They are then cracked to release the kernels, which are then ground into a paste. This paste forms the basis for the oil extraction, which can be done either cold or hot. Cold pressing preserves more nutrients and a refined taste, while hot pressing increases the oil yield. After pressing, the oil is filtered to remove impurities, resulting in a clear, pure oil. In addition to walnut oil, the residual products, such as the shells and husks, can also be valorized, for example as biomass or in artisanal applications. This not only increases the sustainability of the production, but also creates additional revenue streams.

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